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- 20190517_OO_student8_Transcript0...

File outline

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1 [00:00:00]
2
3 [BEGIN TASK 34A]
4 R: Ok, so you may not compile. The first question I wanna ask you, or maybe you can read it yourself.
5 S: Describe the purpose of this code, and if the code was written in a function, give a proper name for the function.
6 R: So I don't want you to tell me what, first read it, tell me, think out loud, tell me what you're thinking when you read
  it, what do you see...
7 S: Ok, so it has a list which would probably be a parameter, if it was a function, then it takes the first value and then
  looks for each of the values, if the value's smaller than the current... It determines the minimum of the list. Ehm...
  yeah, and if the value that we're currently looking at is smaller than the one that we have stored so far, it replaces it.
  So this is basically a function that determines the minimum of the rainvalues list, so if it would be placed in a function,
  it would be something like intmain and would take an integer array as an argument instead of a hard coded one, and would
  return it instead of print.
8 [END TASK 34A]
9 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 34A]
10 R: Perfect. Yeah, the reason why I asked you if it would be placed in a function, because I don't want, so people would
    tell me, well the printed becomes the value of... And I don't want you to read to me what is said but exactly, perfect, you
    said it's the minimum of the list. Awesome. Ok, I'd like you to answer these three questions about it.
11
12 [00:01:21]
13
14 R: How difficult did you find the programme code while you were reading, did you, was it very difficult to understand what
    the code did?
15 S: Well, it's a pretty standard function, so, ehm... In this case not really difficult code. It also doesn't use very
    difficult concepts. It's sort of, what, an enhanced for-loop over the array and an if-statement, so it's also not really
    complex code, so it also...
16 R: You called it an enhanced for-loop, why do you call it an enhanced for-loop?
17 S: An enhanced for-loop, because it goes over the array, and a normal for-loop is the one with, in i is zero, and this, we
    learned that in object-orientation and [?]. And ehm, the instructions, well, was, I did know what I had to do.
18
19 [END DISCUSS TASK 34A]
20 [00:02:05]
21 [BEGIN TASK 34B]
22
23 R: Ok, perfect. Same type of question but a little bit different.
24 S: Ok. Rainvalue... Ok, it's the same thing... Int i equals zero, then over the length, so this also goes over the entire
    array, so i is [not?] a subscript into the rainvalues, ok if it's greater than the current one, and then increment i, this
    is the while equivalent to a normal for-loop, and it's the maximum function of the rainvalues.
25 [END TASK 34B]
26 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 34B]
27 S: Ehm... For this one, I imagine it would be more difficult if we didn't have a course in C where we learned how, a course
    on how a for-loop is done in assembly. Because, in the processes course we had how a for-loop is done in assembly. And set
    the i, while-loop, and ++ is basically the same as writing the three things in a for-loop. So, yeah, it's basically the
    same thing, except greater than, instead of less than.
28 R: Yeah. And why do you, why are you relating to what you learned in assembly?
29 S: Because in the first course, the processes course, we also had to translate a for-loop to our, to our assembly language
    basically. And it was the same thing, you set a certain register to zero, then you increment it after each one, and jump if
    it's greater.
30 R: Ok. Very good, this was the first code I gave you, with the for-each, this is the second one. I'm gonna ask you, can you
    tell me which one did you find more difficult? Oh wait, first let's do this one.
31 S: Well, not very complex, but it was more complex, it's written in a more complex way.
32 R: What makes it more complex?
33 S: Well, the fact that it uses the int while, the int i, the while and the ++, so it splits up a loop control over three
    different parts, instead of concentrating it all into for-statement. So, I'd say this is more complex, also more complex
    than it should be.
34 R: Because?
35 S: Well, in this sense, if you wanted to change, for example the variable name for whatever reason, if you needed to change
    something in the loop, you have three places that you need to check. And it's not, and if the while-loop for example, if
    the body became bigger, it would be impossible to see everything at once, lack context, and in the for-loop it's all
    collected in the parentheses. But... not that complex and the explanation, it was the same task, so...
36
37 [00:04:46]
38
39 R: So the explanation was just the same. Ok. So now I'm giving you both pieces of code, this is the one with the for each
    and this is the while, and maybe you could put it, tell me which one do you find more difficult than the other? Can you
    order it?
40 S: I would say this one is more difficult. Mainly because, exclusively because it used the, basically expanded for-loop
    instead of a proper one.
41 [END DISCUSS TASK 34B]
42 [BEGIN TASK 34C]
43 R: All right, perfect. You're probably gonna laugh when you see this one, or recognize it at least.
44 S: Ok, it... It counts how many values in there are zero, so since it's rainvalues, basically how many days there were
    where it didn't rain. And, yeah, it's just a standard for-loop over the entire array, and, checks whether they're zero.
45 R: OK.
46 [END TASK 34C]
47 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 34C]
48 S: So, not much to it.
49
50 [00:05:42]
51
52 R: Yeah, so I wrote down, "how many days it didn't rain". How about the programme code of this one, how difficult did you
    find that? How complex?
53 S: Well, I'd say just as complex as the other for-loop, so as the one A, maybe a bit more because it actually uses the int,
    the index into the rain, where there's no need for knowing which index it is, because you can also just go over the
    elements themselves. So, and, the instruction, it's the same thing.
54 R: Ok, and if you order it...
55 S: Between the first two. So in the middle. A bit more complex than the enhanced for-loop because it, well, it uses the
    index where there's no need, but easier to read than this one [the while], because it contains all the things that
    controlled the loop in one place.
56 R: Yeah. That's why I said you'd laugh, because you said, well here you have what you said it causes you to recognize that
57 S: Yeah.
58 R: The i is zero, that's the first thing here
59 S: and then the second one, and then the third one
60 R: and then it's the same but it's split up. Interesting. OK, thank you very much.
61 [END DISCUSS TASK 34C]
62
63 [00:06:56]
64
65 R: Now I'm gonna ask you to type some code in. So, maybe you wanna read...
66 [00:07:00]
67 [BEGIN TASK 81 (ATTEMPT A)]

```

Track changes is off

You: S1: construct familiarity
Jan 9, 2024 5:40 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S6: while harder/error prone than for
Jan 9, 2024 5:41 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S6: while harder/error prone than for
Jan 9, 2024 5:42 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S8: Foreach overzichtelijjk/compact
Jan 9, 2024 5:43 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S2: FOR understandable
Jan 9, 2024 5:46 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S8: FOREACH overzichtelijjk/compact
Jan 9, 2024 5:46 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: O4NEG recalls familiar plan
Jan 9, 2024 5:49 AM • Edit

68 S: of the maximum... How many days the maximum amount of rain... Ok. Ehm... I could, well I'm not supposed to just use the fact that it's 76, right? Like, it should also work with...

69 R: No, this is an example. So I want you to, it has to work for any...

70 S: Given array. Ok, so what I, I could do this two ways, I could first determine the maximum and then count how often it occurs in the array. That would be one way, but that requires me to go over the array two times, which for larger arrays might not, or would not be the most efficient way to do it. So what I would do is I'd make two variables, I'm just going to do it actually... int count is zero... and int max is minus one, basically to show a value that will never be legal in this, in the example it would always be non-negative, and then for... For int... elem of the rainValues... I'm just going to, what I'm going to do is I'm gonna go over the entire array and reset the maximum each time I find a new maximum value, and if I don't find, so basically for each value it's gonna be either less than the old maximum, in which case it doesn't matter, it's gonna be equal to the old maximum which can increment the count by 1, or it's gonna be bigger in which case I change the old maximum and it set the count to 1, because then if we to count exactly 1 element in this case. If... elem is greater than zero, no not greater than zero... Greater than max... max equals, max is equal to elem... and count is equal to 1, because we have already seen one instance of this. Else if elem is equal to the maximum, just increment the count by 1, there's no need to update the maximum if it's the same, and if it's less than the maximum, I actually don't increment the count and don't change max, so I don't need a case for this. So the else case can just be empty, if the element's smaller than the maximum. So I think, and well, we return, out, system.out, obviously the count, println, count... Did I miss a semi-colon? OK.

71 [00:10:08]

72 [END TASK 81 (A)]

73 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 81 (A)]

74 R: So now you've been able to reduce it to one for-loop, because first you said you could do a for and then...

75 S: Yeah I could just use the maximum function, like arrays of max of something, but... [refers to calling max function first to determine max would require one iteration of the array]

76

77 [00:10:20]

78

79 R: And now you... Ok, good. The same questions again.

80 S: This one says untangling code.

81 R: Yeah, that's the name of the research.

82 S: Ok, because I'm not untangling anything, I thought...

83 R: Yeah, never mind that.

84 S: Well, I don't really think... Well, I imagine it would be easier to read probably if I did two passes over the array, so I went with performance over readability here. Ehm... So I'd say this is actually more complex than the examples before, probably.

85 R: What makes it harder?

86 S: Well, the fact that it goes over the array and then that's something dependent on what the action is because the only one where we had this, it was always only a simple comparison, but now it actually does something else depending on what the element is, depending on the max, and it maintains two different variables.

87 R: So you're talking about the else if makes it more complex, and the fact that you have the two variables, which two variables do you mean?

88 S: Count and max, that's, yeah, it's two variables now that you change, sometimes.

89 R: Ok, and so having the else if makes it more complex than if you also have an if?

90 S: Yeah, that's the thing, that's an if-statement, but this one is an else-if, I feel like the logic behind this one would be more complex than the [set?]. Like, I would usually if I wrote this for someone else, I would add a comment. I'm not adding a comment here because it's gonna be deleted as soon as you close the window, but... [laughs].. So, ehm, well the concepts and definitions, still just the for-loop and if-statement, and two variables, so it's not really more complex, in terms of what I used and the... Yeah, I knew exactly what I needed to do.

91

92 [00:12:12]

93

94 R: Yeah. Can I ask, can you order it?

95 S: Ehm... Probably in here as well, because I feel like this one is really, if you don't know that this is basically just a for-loop, but you actually try to, like you've never seen a for-loop expanded out like this, I imagine it would be, it would take a while until you realise what it is.

96 [END DISCUSS TASK 81]

97 [00:13:02]

98

99 S: Well, ehm... Determining the max... Should be, the arrays has a .max function, like, in that case I could just use the...

100 R: And if it doesn't, could you determine it without using the max function?

101

102

103

104 [00:18:06]

105

106 R: Ok, perfect, thank you. Ehm... Then I have another task for you.

107 [00:18:10]

108 [BEGIN TASK 83]

109 S: Ok. [reads text] the index of the first rainy day and the last rainy day... If there are no rainy days... Ok, so the first rainy day is just one where the value is not zero, I guess, and ok, the first rainy day until the last rainy day... Hm... Well I can't use an enhanced for-loop at least, because I need the index actually, so I need a normal for-loop... And then, well, the thing is the last rainy day, it would probably be easiest to find it if I go like, backwards. Yeah, I think it would be easiest to just, if I go backwards over the array. Like I start once at the front and go forward and once at the end and go backwards. It's probably not the fastest way but else I would need the variable to keep track of the state, like whether I'm in a rainy section or not, I need to go through the entire array... Well actually it's still faster if I go forwards once and backwards one other time. Because else I need to go to the end to find the last element. So... and if there are no rainy days, print error message. Ok. In that case, again... So first off, I'm gonna declare two variables for the... For the first day and for the last day, and I'm gonna initialize both to minus one. Ehm... So I know, because I'm supposed to give an error message if there is no last day, if there is no rainy day, and if I see, if I go through the first for-loop and I see that the index is still minus one, because there was no rainy day, then I can print out the error message. Actually I don't need to search for the last one in that case, so first off go over it, now with a normal for-loop because I need to store the index, i is less than rainValues.length... Ehm, i++... And, ehm... Well, we don't care if it's raining or not... Well, we don't care much if it rains, so if rainValues[i] is greater than zero... Then set first day to i and break. Because, when we find the first day and if it kept iterating on it would find the other rainy days as well, so this stops the for-loop. You could also do this and I imagine our professor would prefer that way with a variable that says finished or not, and then sets it true, but I personally prefer breaking out of a loop. Guess it's a difference of style. Then the error message... If first day is still minus one, then ehm... print an error message. So system.out.println... Ehm, an error message, so system.err... or if this was a function I would turn exception, because for subfunction it would not be a good style to ehm... just print something to a console, when an error occurs, so error not exception. In this case, system.out.println... Ehm... there are no rainy days... Ehm, and actually return, which in this case quits the programme, but also in subfunction it would make sure that, well, in the subfunction of an exception it doesn't matter, but this case it makes sure that doesn't also try to go backwards through the entire array, because we already know there is no rainy day. And now I'm just going to copy this, cause, well a part of it stays the same, except that i is now rainValues.length, minus one, i is greater or equal to zero and i is minus minus, which is a loop that goes backwards over the entire array. And then rainValues is i and in this case, ehm, last day. Ok, and then we... print... And since it's, I got a format here, which has the numbers in the middle, I'm actually gonna use print f, with ehm, first day and last day as arguments, I could also do string plus integer, because it converts it automatically, but this is pretty much why formattings were invented, and adding a string to an integer is something that not all languages handle quite well, actually Java is fine, Java does it the same way, yeah. And index of...

110 R: Yeah I was just about to say, you can cut-paste if you want...

111 S: Except of course we're replacing these with a percentage d... And I think, yeah this is... and because this is quite long, I'm gonna push these two to the next line, so you can still see what it's effectively printing out. So it's now the content of the message, even if you don't see the entire formatting, so yeah, this...

112 [END TASK 83]

113 [00:24:34]

114 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 83]

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: O9 considers efficiency
Jan 9, 2024 5:49 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S13 integrating multiple plans/merging harder
Jan 9, 2024 5:51 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S22 variable interactivity (effecting each other)
Jan 9, 2024 5:52 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S20 #variables to think about
Jan 9, 2024 5:53 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S20 #variables to think about
Jan 9, 2024 5:53 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S16 multiple branches/jumps (selections)
Jan 9, 2024 5:53 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: O6 considers/knows construct - plan combo
Jan 9, 2024 6:36 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: NOT O5 lacking appropriate design beforehand
Jan 9, 2024 6:36 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: O9 considers efficiency
Jan 9, 2024 6:37 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: NOT O3 lacking terminate plan
Jan 9, 2024 6:37 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: O4NEG recalls familiar plan
Jan 9, 2024 6:37 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: O9 considers efficiency
Jan 9, 2024 6:38 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

114 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 83]
115
116 R: Ok, excellent. Then have a look at your code, and the task of the program code...
117 S: Well I'd say, especially what people, what also is the most complex part here is the ehm, the reversed for-loop because that, like I think that would be the most difficult thing, ehm... what it does I imagine is pretty clear, because ehm, this is a standard for-loop and the variable names, I'd say also give you a certain amount of guidance. Like, what first day stores, if you set it equal to the index variable it's pretty obvious, if you don't know what it's supposed to do, and, yeah, I mean, this one documents itself with what the problem is, so this already tells us when is this if given, so I imagine the most difficult part of this would be the backwards form.
118 R: Yeah, because you have a forward for-loop and a backwards, you say the backwards is more trickier than the first.
119 S: Yeah, it's trickier to read, because you need to make sure that you both don't get, use rainValues.length as an index and that you also remember to use, to check the first element, for example if only the first day is a rainy day, and I've typed i greater zero, then it wouldn't work properly. So with a backwards loop, it's not as nice to write, because the index starts at zero, not one. So I'd say this is more complex than the ones before, also more complex definitions and concepts than the one before.
120 R: What makes it...?
121 S: Mainly the backwards for-loop I imagine, like that's gonna be the biggest problem in understanding. I don't feel like this is also gonna be the example the next to students to check what it does. And yeah, the task was a bit more difficult to understand than the previous one, I'd say, not understand, but it was a more complex task than the previous ones.
122 [00:26:41]
123
124 R: Ok, but this is about, did you know what I was asking, did you know what you had to do...
125 S: Yeah, I knew what I had to do, but it's a more difficult task than the ones before.
126 R: Ok, and what made it more difficult?
127 S: Well for one, that we had to actually check whether it's a sensible input, because we had to check whether there are any rainy days, which otherwise, if it didn't explicitly say this, I imagine a lot of programs would happily print out index of first rainy day minus one, index of last rainy day minus one. And yeah, that we actually have to keep track of the indices, because we need them, we can't use an enhanced for-loop for this. Ehm... Since we aren't allowed to use library functions in this one, since I'm not allowed to use a library function, that doesn't matter typically, but I would also think about doing is, ehm, do a forwards for-loop for the second one as well, but use arrays of reverse, because that both tells you what it does and also is easier to read, but at the same time, arrays of reverse has a pretty bad runtime, O of n I think, expect, so it might also slow the programme down significantly, if you have more than eight rain values.
129 R: Because, when you started off, you wanted to use a function, what was the max, to find the max of a list I think. would that have made it easier for you?
130 S: Not so much for me, the max function is easy enough to write, but it makes it easier for someone to read, because then they don't have to think, what does the for-loop do, they just see ok, arrays.max, obviously that finds the max element in the array.
131 R: So writing is not that hard but it makes it easier, yeah...
132 S: It makes it easier to write because it states the intention, yeah. I could've also added a comment to first find the maximum and then a second comment, now check how many elements are equal to this maximum. So that is something, so I would need to comment it because it isn't a function.
133 [00:28:49]
134
135 R: Ok, and how can we order it? Where would you place it?
136 S: Ehm... I would actually place this one, maybe because the forward and the backwards loop, at the bottom of the list so far. So I'd say this is the most complex one so far. But I also see that there's still some left on the scoreboard.
137 R: Yeah, no, we're not gonna do all of them. Don't worry, I'm not gonna keep you here that long.
138 S: Oh, I don't have anything else to do today, so...
139 [00:29:24]
140
141 R: Ok, ehm... One or two more questions.
142 [00:29:27]
143 [BEGIN TASK 90 (A)]
144 S: Ok, ehm... Horizontal bar chart, oh thank God, because if the next one is a vertical bar chart, that's gonna be way more complex. Ehm... actually I don't want to do this one. Ok, ehm, so in each line basically, ok, so even if I just say out loud what it should do, for each day, it should print out how many stars there are. So, naturally it would, yeah, it would seem that a for-loop, I put here, so for ehm, int ehm, rain amount or something... It's a shortened variable, I don't think it needs that big of... nice name but well... for each rain amount, ehm... I'm just thinking how I do... Yeah I wanna print out like, now rain amount contains the number of asterisks I want to print, but I just remembered that I can't do, or that Java doesn't have string times integer. Because I wanted to do like string asterisk times...
148 R: Where do you know that from?
149 S: Javascript and Python both have that one. But ehm, Java doesn't as far as I know, and there's also no string function for repeating it. So I need to, well I guess I need to do a second, yeah I need to do in a for-loop, can I do this... I'm just thinking, would I need to do an, in a for-loop, for all of those, or what I can actually, ehm... Sorry, I'm just thinking because I can do it obviously within a for-loop, like for i equals zero until we have reached rain amount with an asterisk, and then else I print a new line, but I also can get, could reuse these, yeah because it's only simple integers. I can actually reuse these values, so ehm, for objects this would be a problem, because it would only cover the [?], but because this is an integer, what I can do is while, rain amount is greater than zero, actually... system.out.println... ehm, asterisk... where is asterisk on this keyboard? And then ehm, rain amount minus and, rain amount--, so this goes over the entire, actually, my bad, not system.out.println, just system.out.print, and then ehm, system.out.println this time with no arguments, which just makes it go to the new line.
150 [END TASK 90 (A)]
151 [00:32:43]
152 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 90 (A)]
153 S: We could also, depending on how bad, actually I'm, yeah, actually I'm going to do that right now, I just remembered that this might be a problem, because I print out for each asterisk, so if you for example use something this, while another programme is also running on the same console, it would interleave the stars with the other output, so I would actually ehm... A, what am I gonna do here... Ehm... A string builder actually because for string the behaviour is too bad... String builder is b, is a new string builder...
154 R: Ok, you don't have to go into that, it's very good that the level that you're thinking at...
155 S: Yeah I was thinking because it'd print out each star that's only, I/O is a pretty slow operation as well, so system.out.println...
156 R: I'm not that interested in this. Ok, I'm very interested in something, because the first time you told me ok, I'm gonna do the for rain amount, and then you said I can do another for-loop to go through, and instead you chose to do the while.
157 S: Yeah I chose to do the while, because this way we don't have another variable. Because what you would need to do otherwise, is for int i, equals zero, int i is less than rain amount, i++ and print out a star. which does the same thing, obviously, and then print out a new line. But that would be another variable, that we're iterating over and well it's, it's not really more complex than just looking at it, I imagine it would still be easier to do, not to do but to read because here we have again the greater than zero and then a --, so it would actually rewrite it to for-loop. Ehm...
158 [00:37:41]
159
160 [CONT. DISCUSS TASK 90 (A)]
161 R: Ok. If we look at the first one that you made, the while-loop, I'm gonna ask you to answer the questions for both of them. If you look at your for-while, how complex is the program code that you see there?
162 S: It's a bit over-complex, because it reuses rain amount as a count at the same time as a data, so, and when I think about I'm not even sure whether I'm, yeah, it should not modify the written array, but I would actually need to test it, to see whether it does. So ehm... it's both more complex and for objects it would not be safe, either. Like, for example if you have atomic, if you use atomic integers or anything that has an integer property, you count will decrease by one or something, then it would actually modify the original object, which obviously, the function shouldn't modify its input if it's not explicitly saying so. So I'd say, it wasn't hard, I could decode it, ehm... I'd also say it's a bit more complex than it needs to be.

You: S12 difficulty tweaking plan
Jan 9, 2024 6:42 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

You: S10 tweaking construct (parameters)
Jan 9, 2024 6:41 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

You: S24 # tasks subplot
Jan 9, 2024 6:43 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

You: O6 considers/knows construct - plan combo
Jan 9, 2024 6:43 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

You: O9 considers efficiency
Jan 9, 2024 6:43 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

You: O4 NOT recalls familiar plan
Jan 9, 2024 6:46 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

You: O9: considers efficiency: reusing variable
Jan 10, 2024 7:29 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

You: O9: considers efficiency
Jan 10, 2024 7:32 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

You: S5: WHILE intuitive
Jan 10, 2024 7:33 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

You: S23 vars with multiple roles / re-use
Jan 9, 2024 6:48 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

164 R: But is it more complex than the examples we've been doing so far?
165 S: Not particularly, no, especially not more complex than this one [refers to 34b: read while task], which did the same thing basically, but is probably why it started doing...
166 R: And with this one you meant the...
167 S: 34b, the one that had the while and i++. Well, concepts and definitions... well, it's still just the for and the while-loop, so I wouldn't say it's any more complex in that sense, like an enhanced-for and a while-loop, but it's not more complex... Kinda miss the range function from Python right now, but ehm... So I'd say not more complex, and ehm, I knew what to do, mainly because of the example which was very helpful and telling because I had an example value, and example output, and it's quite a good way for me to know what I should do. That's the same for both.

168 [00:40:03]
169
170
171 R: Ok, and before you fill this one in, tell me where you would order this solution, the top solution, with the for and while.
172 S: Well, with the for-loop, I'd actually put it even slightly beneath this one, because it has a for-loop and then is basically, like half of a for-loop and then expanded out, and it's yeah...
173 R: Ok, and it's more difficult than this one because?
174 S: Well, mainly because of the fact that it's inside another for-loop, so you'd need to keep track, you need to realise what is going on here, like, that it actually does this for each one independently of the others, but that's not entirely obvious here. Because you change something about it, like you say for each element, then change rain amount, so it might look like you modify the array in some way, which it doesn't, but it might look like that. So, ehm, I'd say that makes it more complex than it actually should be, or more complex to read.
175 R: Yeah, I'm not asking what it should be, but more complex than the ones before now. Ok...
176 [END DISCUSS TASK 90 (A)]
177
178 [00:42:55]
179
180
181 R: Ok, excellent. Then I have one more question for you. Merging two lists.
182 [BEGIN TASK 88 (A)]
183 [00:43:01]
184
185 S: Ok, ehm... Oh it actually has, eh, stops, method stops, which I can use.
186 R: Yes, if you want I have two tips...
187 S: Yeah, either array or arrayLists.
188 R: So I wasn't sure which one you'd prefer to use...
189 S: [reads text] [mumbles] enough, ehm... [reads text] Ok, they are always of the same length, because else it would be problematic. So, ehm... since you don't have given, I'm just gonna copy the one for arrays I think. [silence for 9 seconds] And the first thing I'm actually gonna do is rainValues1.length times two, because else if you like, add another rainValue it's not gonna work anymore, so that's generally not good, like you're relying on the requirements. Ehm... Ehm, well, now, ehm... actually, yeah, since I need to iterate over both and I want to keep them in touch I can't use the enhanced for-loop, like I could iterate over one, but I'd still need to keep an index into the other one, and increment it each time so I might as well just keep one comment indexed for both of them. So... for int i is zero, i is less than, I'm just gonna use the first one, rainValues1.length... i++ and then rainValuesMerged and I'm thinking... What is the index in two rainValues, might wanna put it on because actually there's an easier way to do this, I'm actually gonna increment it by two each time, because otherwise I'd need to multiply the index and this way I actually like, go two into it each time. Ehm, although that way I can't, actually then I need to iterate over rainValuesMerged.length, because else it stops after half of the array. So this now iterates effectively over the rainValuesMerged and I know it always has an even length, obviously because it is a multiple of the length of another array, and then i is the even one, so the first one of the two, which should be from the first list, and then i, index plus one is the one from the second list, I should put it and then plus and then... yeah. So i is the second... i is the same as... this way, ehm... yeah, that works. Ehm, rainValues1, i over two, because for example, if I have i equals to here, this should have the element at index one, rainValues1, so ehm, I want it like this. And then the same things, I'm gonna copy it, except rainValues2, and I'm using the fact that i is an integer, plus one this one, ehm... plus one. Ehm, because this way if it's at one, it runs down to zero when dividing by two, so I guess the first element in this array, and at three it then gets the next element, so it always gets the right element. And that's actually it.

190 [00:47:35]
191 [END TASK 88 (A)]
192 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 88 (A)]
193
194 S: And looking at it I'm also really glad I do some graphics because processing of p5.js, because there you often have it that you will need to iterate over multiple arrays, and with graphics, especially from one dimension into two dimensions you get used to manipulating array subscripts a bit more, like I can just basically visualize them as two rectangles. And then I have rainValuesMerged as a one-D array and those are just the individual columns. So... yeah. Obviously, if you had more than two, you would actually need to adjust it a bit but, even then it's not too bad actually, you just need to replace two at every step by how many values you, value-lists you have. So the task... [reads text] The array subscripts, you would need to go through, obviously, and like, at least for the first like, four indices, you actually need to see what does it do for those values, fine as well from zero to three, to actually realise what is happening here, so ehm... The thing is, if I went with rainValues1.length and i plus equals one, I would need to multiply by two here, and plus one, and that, you would still need to check where the index are you currently, so it's not going to be any easier to read.
195 R: And how about understand, because when they read they like, when you were writing the programme you had to think about how it would round off as well. would you say that integer values...
196 S: Yeah it's just floor division, that is something if I iterate it over one length, I wouldn't have that. Ehm that's true, so it would not have that problem, because multiplying is more straightforward than dividing, and ehm... actually it wouldn't be too big a change either but... Yeah, like I think it might be a bit simpler, but I'm not actually sure it would make a difference. Like it's actually short enough that I can just write out. Come to think of it.

197 [00:52:17]
198 [CONT. DISCUSS TASK 88 (A)]
199
200 R: Oh well that's not... Ok, what I found interesting is that while you were writing this code, you said ok, values in two integers, so I have to, so it looked like you stepped out of the code and you're like oh, floor division, now it's gonna round off, if you think what's gonna happen with it and then it's...
201 S: Yeah I still need to think it through.
202 R: Yeah you think about it, I know you're doing at that moment, are you thinking about what happens with these two values and how, or with the two indexed values...
203 S: Yeah effectively was checking whether it's correct, but like, for index zero this goes, these go to zero obviously and then these go to one, and then they go to here.
204 R: You're doing a trace in your head actually.
205 S: Yeah I'm evaluating like, for the first few iterations, I'm looking whether it makes sense or whether it actually gives the results that I want.
206 R: Yeah, and then when you're happy with it, you're like, oh yeah. So that's what you say, ok it works well, and then you went on to the next... Ehm, so I see that you really step out and at that moment it seemed to me, like you weren't interested in the rest of the code anymore, you were really focussing on this one, is that true?
207 S: Kind of, yes.
208 R: No it's good, because you're able to do that, I see a lot of students who are still, they have the list in their head, index in their head and they're trying to do everything at the same time. And then they're like, aah, help!
209 S: No, no, just to look like, ok, this is zero, then this is one, the zero, zero, one, zero, for two it's two, one, three, one, then I was like, ok that's exactly what we wanted to check.

210 [00:53:47]
211
212 [CONT DISCUSS TASK 88 (A)]
213
214 R: ok, all right. Let's choose one of them, shall we choose the bottom one? Choose the bottom one and tell me what you think.
215 S: Should I delete the too one then?

You: S17: nesting hard
Jan 10, 2024 7:43 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
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You: S18 nested conditional hard (harder than nested loop)
Jan 10, 2024 7:47 AM • Edit
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You: S22: variable interactivity
Jan 10, 2024 7:43 AM • Edit
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You: S6: WHILE harder, more error prone
Jan 10, 2024 7:46 AM • Edit
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You: O6 considers/knows construct-plan combo
Jan 10, 2024 7:49 AM • Edit
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You: O4NEG recalls familiar plan
Jan 10, 2024 8:06 AM • Edit
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You: S14 (novel) algorithm explicit thought/hard
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You: S22 variable interactivity (effecting each other)
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You: NOT S21 unconfident reasoning about control flow
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216 R: No, we'll do both of them, ok?
217 S: Oh, also, yeah sure. It's just, if you only use one of them, I imagine you'd store, so like what I type in...
218 R: Oh, I'm gonna store it all, I'm just gonna copy it into two different things. So this one is the merged list... So start with the top one and look at your...
219 S: Well, the concepts and definitions in there aren't that much, they aren't any different, actually I would say it's a bit tricky, not complex in terms, you wouldn't know what it does, but it's tricky in terms of the $i+1$ equals two, because I imagine a lot of people will not notice that at first.
220 R: Ok, I think that's more program code than concepts. The concepts is more the indices, the fact that you have to think, you have to use the indices, because we haven't been doing that very much, have we?
221 S: No no, typically we didn't really use the indices for anything...
222 R: To manipulate them now.
223 S: Yeah. Ehm... So I'd say it's more...
224 R: So the program code is more complex and what makes it more complex?
225 S: Well, actually that for one you need to check with the plus equals two and then the careful thing with the indices that you need to make sure, I imagine that's probably if you read it I imagine that's what takes you the longest time in understanding this.
226 R: And you say you have to take care of that because it's different than the standard, the standard plus plus.
227 S: Yeah, right, and I imagine if someone reads this through, they wouldn't at first think it overwrites the values or something, it doesn't but, people would be confused by why $i+1$ and $i+1$ one if you increment i anyways, so ehm, yeah. I imagine that would be complex, but as far as the actual content, as far as the structure goes, ehm, I'd also say a bit more because the i 's divided by two. So that also says, people would probably stumble over that. Like, wait, that's a floating point, no that's not an integer, wait it actually rounds off, so like, I imagine people would need to actually remember that it is, that it rounds off, not everyone does that. Like, some people would actually expect this to give floating point, like float or double if it's ehm... if it isn't an actual integer. Which would be a fun but ehm, so I'd also say this is more difficult, yeah. And the instructions and explanations weren't clear, no not really. I mean, you need to be sure of course that they are the same length, because else the behaviour is different but yeah, again.
228
229 [00:57:04]
230
231 R: Did you understand from the description that you had to take first the 25, first this one and then that one and then that one?
232 S: Yeah, actually just the input and output, seeing them at the same time, already was quite helpful. Like, since you said you're a teacher, that's something I would've liked to have at my assignments in high school as well. Like, seeing, except for an example in- and output. Because there's a problem, the description can be quite abstract for someone who sees it for the first time. Ehm... But no, actually this was quite a clear explanation. Of course a bit harder task but, yeah.
233
234 [00:57:47]
235
236 S: Oh, you said that was the last one, right?
237
238 [01:00:38]
239 [CONT DISCUSS TASK 88 (A)]
240 R: Yes, but I want you to order it if you can, for your second one. Now you look at this one, and could you tell me where you would place that?
241 S: Ehm... Well it's, the thing is... Yeah, like, this one, what I imagine would surprise someone is that even though it iterates over apparently the `rainValues1`, that it's also influencing the `rainValues`, or it also uses the `rainValues2` array, so someone might think, why is it you're using the second array, if it only iterates over the first, can't iterate over both simultaneously. Actually it could iterate over the first one, then the second one, but there's no use in that actually, really, realistically. But I imagine someone need to think wait, it iterates over `rainValues1`, but why does it then use `rainValues2`, i plus one? So I imagine that would confuse people but the same time I feel like it's still as easy now as a multiplication and the simple for-loop, I'd actually rank it above the one with the horizontal bar chart.
242 R: All right, excellent.
243 S: Would you mind if I looked at the last one?
244 R: Yeah sure, but that's the last of the average rainfall, it's one that comes that we see in research a lot, students have a lot of difficulty with finding the average, and what usually happens is that they, well maybe you want to explain, you don't have to type it in.
245 S: Well, I just have a for-loop because I only...
246 [END DISCUSS TASK 88 (A)]
247 [01:02:22]
248 [BEGIN TASK 89]
249 R: Well if you want to, do you want to do it?
250 S: I was gonna say... It's not gonna take long, just a second... and i equals zero... never mind that, I can use an enhanced for-loop. ehm... `int rainValue of rainValues`, ehm... `int amount` is zero, and one named `sum` is zero, because like, I need to keep track of the amount of values I have and the one in `sum` cause I not, I can't use `array.length` because this one would ehm, then also divide by eight so I need to keep track of both the amount and that, so ehm... If `rainValue` is greater than zero, and it don't actually give you every course, so yeah... I don't need an else here because if it's less than zero we just skip over that element, but if the `rain` value is bigger than the `amount++` and `runningSum+` equals `rain` value... so yeah. And then I'd say... and then I'm just gonna write it down. Ehm... for the time being... `return ehm...` and now there's the tricky thing, because it might be that all of them are negative. Like, the entire array only has negative values, or zero, and that way if `amount` would still be zero, so I need to check that. `Amount` is zero... if so `return zero`, because that's the best you can give for an average of an empty array. Else `runningSum over amount...` so in this case the time you operate it because yeah, over an empty array, technically the average is meaningless but still zero is the best I can give. Actually maybe negative values if I, well there is none, but yeah.
251 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 89]
252 R: And how would you find your program code now?
253 S: Not all too complex, ehm... it's a normal for-loop with an if-statement in it, basically no worse than what we've seen, which one was it actually, what we've seen here for the 34a, which I actually stored at the very top, so... It's not really a complex programme, and the only thing that I could imagine someone needs to take a second look at is the amount, also I just remembered something else, which is a problem, ehm... So I have to fix it... Ehm, double `runningSum` because else the ehm... `runningSum over amount` might, would be rounded off and we don't want that for an average. It shouldn't be rounded off. If we use a round-off average, we can get that, but it, you should cast it to `int` himself.
254 [01:06:08]
255 [END TASK 89]
256
257 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 89]
258 R: And so you're saying, yeah the construct is just as much, yeah, but there's, because in 34a you're saying we have a for-loop, a for each and an if in it. And here you say, you have one variable more
259 S: Yeah I put another variable, that's not... I think necessarily, but ehm... I don't think, again, I feel like the variable names already say what is meant. Like, if the `rainValues` are greater than zero, the `amount` increments by one. Then obviously it's increment, then it means that the amount of days where the `rainValue` was greater than zero. And which reminds me, greater than or equal to zero [`types > into >=`], because it's set on non-negative values. So, ehm, yeah. That's the thing, if you don't have, ehm, you can't test it. You miss this, but eh, yeah.
260 R: And how about your return statement?
261 S: What do you mean? Yeah, or print, I don't know, this won't compile, because it's a void function but returns, but ehm... typically this would be a subfunction, so you would return.
262 R: Ok, because you say it's not, can you say where you would place it?
263 S: Place it... I think the fact that you have these variables that you need to check what they're doing, would make it a bit more complex than actually ehm... this one. At the same time I don't think really, it's not really complex program, I guess...
264 R: What makes it harder than that one?
265 S: Well, harder than that one, mainly the fact that it takes the two variables it maintains and increments both of them at the same time. Ehm... and harder than this one, also plus the terminal statement, like, I feel like this is a bit complex for a terminal statement because an if-statement it would be overkill, like, if `amount zero return zero else return runningSum amount`. I feel like that would be too much, but at the same time you could do it, some people really don't like this return really [refers to if then else in one line of return statement] but ehm, some of our teachers don't like this

You: S14 (novel) algorithm explicit thought/hard
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You: S1 construct familiarity
Jan 10, 2024 8:21 AM • Edit
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You: S22 variable interactivity (effecting each other)
Jan 10, 2024 8:23 AM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

You: S22 variable interactivity (effecting each other)
Jan 10, 2024 8:24 AM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

You: S14 (novel) algorithm explicit thought/hard
Jan 10, 2024 8:25 AM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

You: S10 tweaking construct (parameters)
Jan 10, 2024 8:25 AM • Edit
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You: O4NEG recalls familiar plan
Jan 10, 2024 8:26 AM • Edit
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You: O6 considers/knows construct-plan combo
Jan 10, 2024 8:26 AM • Edit
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You: O10 minor forget&recall
Jan 10, 2024 8:28 AM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

You: S20 variables to think about
Jan 10, 2024 8:28 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S25 simultaneous tasks
Jan 10, 2024 8:29 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

return, eh, some say it's fine for stuff like this, again it's more manner of taste really, not really a matter of...

266 R: And it's easier than the amount of days maximum, that was you first determined the maximum and then count how many days there is?

267 S: I'd say it's easier than that because it doesn't have, because that also had two variables to maintain but it had a second, like it had an if-else, and you actually reset the value sometimes, but with this, you always just counted up. And again, I'm not a good judge on how complex my programme are, I know that I've worked in code where I thought that's pretty easy to understand, where I've had feedback from my teaching assistants which was that it's really hard to understand, so I'm not the best judge in that.

268

269

270 [01:09:27]

271

272 R: No, but I really like the way that you're talking me through it. You're giving me a lot of information. Excellent. [explains about another programme for students] Oh, can you put the average, I forgot that one.

273 S: Well, the average of some non-negative values... I want to say it's a really easy one, but at the same time I forgot that it's a non-negative, and that it's positive values, so I'm, can't really say it's... So I'd say this is a fairly easy task. Obviously at the same time I'm currently also thinking in the back of my head about our current assignment which is a pattern of a formula evaluation, and compared to that these are all very easy. But to be fair that's also university level, almost last exercise.

274 R: And second course, right.

275

276 S: well, first one for object orientation, but yeah.

277 R: But you've seen lists before.

278 S: Yeah, this would all be function and programming and stuff, we didn't use objects that didn't use helper methods, because it was, I don't know where that could have anywhere, if anything with the asterisk I might have used an helper method for each row, like right number of, right this many asterisk function, but even that's not really necessary. It's a very small function, and it's not a task that you typically need to do, if anything a repeat function would be nice, but eh... So it's not all too complex the code and also not really complex definitions, just for and if. So I'd also say not really complex.

279 [END DISCUSS TASK 89]

280

281 R: ok, excellent, thank you very much.

282

283

284

285

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S24 # tasks subsequent
Jan 10, 2024 8:29 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S15 conditionals incr difficulty
Jan 10, 2024 8:30 AM • Edit

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Resolve Reply

You: O10 minor forget&recall
Jan 10, 2024 8:31 AM • Edit

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